

TRIBAL TOURISM

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Annotation: Today, there are many types of tourism and they are developing rapidly. This article highlights the importance and place of Tribal Tourism, which is considered as a new type in the field of tourism. By increasing interest in this type, people who still live as a community in different parts of the world it is possible to meet, talk with them, learn their way of life, customs and culture, and it is sure to be a new adventure and knowledge for tourists. It is also important to preserve their traditions and cultural heritage.

Key words: Ethno-tourism, ethnic-tourism, indigenous communities, eco-tourism, sustainable-tourism, Ethical Travel Guide, Travel writer.

Аннотация: На сегодняшний день существует множество видов туризма, и они быстро развиваются. В данной статье подчеркивается важность и место племенного туризма, который считается новым видом в сфере туризма. Повышая интерес к этому виду, люди, которые до сих пор живут как сообщества в разных уголках мира, с которыми можно познакомиться, поговорить, узнать их образ жизни, обычаи и культуру, и это обязательно станет новым приключением и познанием для туристов. Также важно сохранить их традиции и культурное наследие.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda turizm sohasing ko'plab turlari mavjud va ular jadallik bilan rivojlanib bormoqda. Ushbu maqolada turizm sohasida yangi tur sifatida qaralayotgan Qabila Turizmining ahamiyati va o'rnini yoritib beriladi. Bu turga qiziqishni oshirish orqali dunyoning turli chekkalarida hali hanuz jamoa bo'lib yashaydigan odamlar bilan uchrashish, ular bilan suxbatlashish, hayot tarzini, urf-odatlarini va madaniyatini o'rganish mumkin, va bu turistlarga yangi sarguzasht va

bilim bo'lishi aniq. Shuningdek, ularning urf-odatlarini va madaniy merosini saqlab qolish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

What exactly is tribal tourism?

Tribal tourism is visiting a place in order to see or meet the indigenous people who live there. "Ethno-tourism" and "ethnic tourism" are sometimes used to describe the same thing. As the name implies, this isn't the same thing as an expedition for anthropological research, but a trip for recreational purposes.

Why are people interested in this kind of tourism?

For some people, it's an educational opportunity – travel is a way of learning more about the world and yourself, and meeting new people can be a part of that. Others feel that, in our globalized age, they'll have a more memorable, authentic experience of a place if they see its indigenous cultures, and for others still, it's simply a voyeuristic exercise: they want to see people whose appearance and way of life look very different to their own.

1-photo. Guarani tribe in jungle, Brazil

What positive effects can it have?

Tribal tourism can have a lot of positive effects. Done sensitively, it can help people learn about and appreciate different ways of life. For indigenous communities, it can facilitate cultural exchange and celebration. And for those that are struggling to maintain their livelihoods and traditions, it's also a way of educating others about their situation, earning some money and playing an active part in the maintenance of their culture.¹

And what about the negative aspects?

Tribal tourism can cause immense damage – and sadly, more often than not, this is the case. There are profound economic, environmental and cultural effects of this kind of tourism, with each usually worsening the other. These issues are complex, and you should make sure you know what's going on before participating in any sort of tribal tourism. The Mursi tribe in Ethiopia's Lower Omo Valley are one example. Following forced resettlements and depletion of the resources on which they depend, they have been forced to use tourism to help make ends meet.

Vehicles full of tourists will arrive in Mursiland, and then briefly stop to take photos before heading back. There's no meaningful exchange, and most Mursi do it grudgingly. Aware that these visitors don't want to emulate their way of life, to learn about them or to get to know them – they just want an exotic souvenir – this makes many of the Mursi feel frustrated and exploited. The irony is that many of the Mursi's adornments aren't part of how they usually dress or decorate themselves, but have been added to better fit the images tourists have come to expect. It's hardly an enriching experience for either side.

Who has the power in this exchange? And how do I know that? Who will my money go to? Have I done my research about these particular people in this particular area, and do I know this visit is safe and enjoyable for both them and me?

¹ Robert Maitland, Peter Newman. World Tourism Cities. (Developing Tourism Off the Beaten Track)23 may 2014. 176 pages.

3-photo. Tribal village in Papua New Guinea

Do be careful not to conflate different issues, too. For instance, just because somewhere sells itself as an ecolodge or green destination, doesn't mean they've taken indigenous land rights and welfare into account. The Rainforest Alliance explains the difference between green tourism, eco-tourism and sustainable tourism, and many of the same concerns apply when considering the tribal or community tourism.

Are there any good examples I can consider?

More and more places are starting to cater to ethical tourists, who are great – but you do need to make sure they practice what they preach. A few well-regulated examples are:

- Aboriginal Australia, Australia: Aboriginal-owned and -run tours throughout the country. Definitely no walks over Uluru here.
- Local Alike, Thailand: Offers community-based tourism in hill-tribe villages of Chiang Rai province.

-Il Ngwesi Lodge, Kenya: Ecolodge and rhino sanctuary in northern Kenya, run by the Maasai who own and manage the land.

Where can I find out more?

As people seek out new travel experiences, it seems likely that this kind of tourism will continue to grow in popularity. Thankfully, there are several groups campaigning with and on behalf of indigenous peoples, helping them amplify their voices in a crowded tourism market and protect their rights and dignity. At the forefront is Survival International, who spearheads campaigns such as the Andaman Trunk boycott, and Tourism Concern, who work to encourage responsible tourism in all areas. Tourism Concern has a growing database of reliable, ethical businesses in their Ethical Travel Guide. The Rainforest Alliance's Green Vacations list is another good source of recommendations for sustainable accommodation and tour operators in South America and Central America and the Caribbean.²

Travel writer Ian Coleman recalls a recent trip to Guatemala, where he saw an example of this. 'There is a village with a statue of a man called Maximon, who has a special spiritual meaning for the local tribe,' he explains. 'The statue is kept indoors, and once a year the locals bring him out and carry him around the village. However, visitors now pay money for them to bring the statue out and carry it around, while they take photographs. As a result, Maximon has lost his original meaning, and is now just another tourist attraction'. So is it possible to experience an exotic culture without harming it in some way? 'With a bit of thought, we can maximize the positive impacts and minimize the negative,' says travel company director Hilary Waterhouse. 'Remember that you are there not only to experience a different culture, but to help it in some way. Tourists bring money to the community, which the community can invest in local projects. However, this does not mean you can act the way you might do back home. The most important thing is to show respect, learn

² <https://www.roughguides.com/article/the-truth-about-tribal-tourism/>

about, and be aware of, local customs and traditions. Always remember you're a guest.'

Dawn Baker, manager of travel company Footprints, runs tours to tribal areas in Peru. 'Good companies specializing in tribal tours are very careful about who they allow on their tours,' she says. 'They won't take anyone they feel is unsuitable' Baker offers reading recommendations so that visitors can read about the country and its cultures. 'The rewards of a trip to this country are priceless, and the more you know in advance, the more priceless they are.' Tribal tourism travellers are often surprised at how basic their facilities are when they get there. 'It's not for everyone, but for me was all part of the experience,' says Jamie White, who has recently returned from a trip to Borneo. 'We stayed in the same huts that everyone was living in, with no running water and no electricity. It was basic, but it was an ethical way to travel. Being comfortable means you use more local resources and so have more of an environmental impact'.

Summary

Tribal tourism is becoming more popular. But at what cost to the locals? Tribal tourism is a relatively new type of tourism. It involves travellers going to remote destinations, staying with local people and learning about their culture and way of life. They stay in local accommodation, share facilities with local people, and join in with meals and celebrations. At the moment, less than one percent of holidays are tribal tourism holidays, but this is set to change. Not everyone is convinced that tribal tourism is a good thing, and opinions are divided. The argument is about whether or not it helps the local population, or whether it exploits them. The main problem is that, because tribal tourism is relatively new, the long-term effects on local populations have not been studied in much detail. Where studies have been carried out, the effects have been found to be negative. For every student, it is very interesting and new knowledge to learn about people living in communities around the world. In this article, the way of life and heritage of the tribal people has been studied, even partially, and their importance in the field of tourism has been considered.

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